

2 720, 1 740, 1 460, 1 340, 1 270, 1 215, 1 130, 1 085, 1 040, 910, 820 and 720 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.95 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.70 (22H, m, saturated methylenes), 2.50 (6H, m, allylic methylenes), 5.40 (2H, m, olefinic protons) and 9.7 (1H, CHO).

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Schmidt Reaction of (25R)-6-Oxo-spirostan-5 α -ol-3 β -alkyl Ether and Beckmann Rearrangement of the Corresponding Ketoxime

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IN view of the immense biological activity of aza steroids¹ and in continuation of our work in this field², we have synthesised aza steroids starting from diosgenin utilising Beckmann rearrangement and Schmidt reaction. In the present communication we report the formation of seco-nitriles from diosgenin.

(25 R)-5-Spirosten-3 β -methyl ether (1a) and (25 R)-5-spirosten-3 β -ethyl ether (1b) were prepared following the reported method³. The treatment of 1a with perbenzoic acid gave a mixture of (25 R)-5 α ,6 α -epoxyspirostan-3 β -methyl ether (2a) and (25 R)-5 β ,6 β -epoxyspirostan-3 β -methyl ether (2b) as indicated by two spots in tlc in benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1), approximately in the ratio of 80 : 20. The repeated fractional crystallisation of the mixture gave α -epoxide (2a), m.p. 205–07°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –325.47; ν_{max} 860 (epoxide)⁴, 1 045 and 1 020 cm^{-1} (C–O); δ 3.4 (3H, s, OCH_3) and 3.7 (1H, m, J 9 Hz, $\text{C}_6\beta$ -H). The mother liquor on further crystallisation gave the β -epoxide (2b), m.p. 210–12°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ +325.47; ν_{max} 865 (epoxide)⁴, 1 030 and 1 015 cm^{-1} (C–O); δ 3.5 (1H, m, J 5 Hz, $\text{C}_6\alpha$ -H). The two epimers were distinguished by their coupling constant (J) values⁵. Similarly, 1b on perbenzoic acid oxidation gave a mixture of (25 R)-5 α ,6 α -epoxyspirostan-3 β -ethyl ether (3a) and (25 R)-5 β ,6 β -epoxyspirostan-3 β -ethyl ether (3b). The above mixture was separated by

repeated fractional crystallisation: the α -epoxide (3a), m.p. 197–99°; ν_{max} 870 cm^{-1} (epoxide); δ 1.58 (3H, t, CH_3 of ethoxy group), 4.2 (2H, q, OCH_2), 4.5 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 12 Hz for 3 α -H)⁶ and 3.6 (1H, m, $\text{C}_6\beta$ -H, J 7 Hz); $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –328.85. the β -epoxide (3b), m.p. 203–05°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ +328.85; ν_{max} 873 cm^{-1} (epoxide); δ 3.8 (1H, m, J 4 Hz, $\text{C}_6\alpha$ -H). The mixture of the epoxides (2a, 2b and 3a, 3b) on chromic acid oxidation in methyl ethyl ketone by Knoff's method⁷ afforded (25 R)-6-oxospirostan-5 α -ol-3 β -methyl ether (4a) and (25 R)-6-oxospirostan-5 α -ol-3 β -ethyl ether (4b), respectively: $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –337.95; ν_{max} 3 470, 3 350 (br, OH) and 1 680 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 4.4 (1H, br m, $W_{1/2}$ 12 Hz, 3 α -H), 5.0 (1H, s, 5 α -OH exchangeable with D_2O) and 2.1 (2H, d, C_7H_2). The negative value of optical rotation indicates that the isomer with $\text{C}_6\alpha$ -OH group has been formed. The exclusive formation of 5 α -isomer is due to its greater stability over 5 β -isomer. However, small quantity of 5 β -isomer in the mother liquor cannot be ruled out.

The Schmidt reaction of the compounds 4a and 4b with sodium azide and concentrated sulphuric acid in benzene solution furnished (25 R)-5,6-seco-6-cyano-5-oxo-spirostan-3 β -methyl ether (6a) and (25 R)-5,6-seco-6-cyano-5-oxospirostan-3 β -ethyl ether (6b), respectively: ν_{max} 2 150 (CN) and 1 670 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.9 (m, C_7H_2) and 3.2 (m, $W_{1/2}$ 9 Hz, $\text{C}_6\beta$ -H). The compounds 4a and 4b on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine gave their respective oximes (5a and 5b): ν_{max} 3 450 and 3 360 cm^{-1} (br, OH); δ 3.5 (s, OH) and 5.7 (s, N–OH exchangeable with D_2O). The Beckmann rearrangement of 5a and 5b with thionyl chloride in dioxane followed by chromatography gave the same seco-nitriles 6a and 6b, respectively, with m.p., m.m.p., ir and nmr spectra identical.

1a; R=OH,
1b; R=C₂H₅

2a (α -epoxide); R=OH,
2b (β -epoxide); R=OH,
3a (α -epoxide); R=C₂H₅,
3b (β -epoxide); R=C₂H₅

4a; R=OH, X=O
4b; R=C₂H₅, X=O
5a; R=OH, X=NOH
5b; R=C₂H₅, X=NOH

6a; R=OH,
6b; R=C₂H₅

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A-60 instrument using TMS as an internal standard.

Preparation of 5 α ,6 α -epoxy (2a, 3a) and 5 β ,6 β -epoxides (2b, 3b) of 3 β -alkyl ether (1a, 1b). A typical experiment: (25 R)-5-Spirosten-3 β -alkyl ether (4 g) was mixed with perbenzoic acid (25 ml, 2 mol) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.1 g) as a catalyst and the mixture was kept at room temperature for 48 h. The mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and extracted with ether-chloroform mixture. The organic extract was washed successively with water, 5% sodium bicarbonate, 5% hydrochloric acid and finally with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent afforded an oily substance which was recrystallised from acetone (3 g, 75%). Its tlc showed two spots in benzene-ethyl acetate (3:1) mixture with relative proportion of α - and β -isomers (80:20). The repeated fractional crystallisation of the mixture (2 g) using ethyl acetate gave the α -epoxide (2a or 3a; 1.6 g, 80%) and the mother liquor on repeated crystallisation gave the β -epoxide (2b or 3b; 0.4 g, 20%).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
			C	H	N
2a	205-07	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₄	75.67 (75.8)	9.90 (9.95)	—
2b	210-12	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₄	75.67 (75.8)	9.90 (9.95)	—
3a	197-99	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₄	75.98 (76.0)	10.04 (10.0)	—
3b	203-05	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₄	75.98 (76.0)	10.04 (10.0)	—
4a	192-94	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₄	73.04 (73.1)	9.56 (9.6)	—
4b	188-90	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₄	73.41 (73.8)	9.70 (9.80)	—
5a	118-20	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₃ N	70.73 (71.2)	9.47 (9.5)	2.94 (3.0)
5b	163-65	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₃ N	71.16 (71.4)	9.61 (9.9)	2.86 (2.9)
6a	170-72	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₄ N	73.52 (73.8)	9.40 (9.6)	3.06 (3.1)
6b	183-85	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O ₄ N	73.88 (74.2)	9.55 (9.8)	2.97 (3.1)

The preparation of (25 R)-6-oxospirostan-5 α -ol-3 β -alkyl ether (4a, 4b), its corresponding oximes (5a, 5b) and seco-nitriles (6a, 6b) were carried out according to the procedure reported earlier².

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Synthesis and Antibacterial Activities of New Quinoline 8-Thioglycollyhydrazones

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QUINOLINE ring derivatives are well-known for their varied spectrum of pharmacological activities. The compounds are claimed to possess antispasmodics¹. The most effective and the best known pharmacology of chincona has been reviewed². Mishra and Saxena³ reported that some quinolines are active against *E. histolytica*. On the other hand, the physiologically active substituted-hydrazones are of immense importance and various hydrazones derivatives are associated with anthelmintic, antifungal and antibacterial activities⁴. A large number of hydrazones have also been used as selective sensitive reagents for determination of copper and other metals⁵. With these in view it was anticipated that quinoline derivatives substituted at 8-position would prove of pharmacological interest. In continuation of our studies on hydrazones as potential drugs, we have synthesised several new quinoline 8-thioglycollyhydrazones (Scheme 1) in which the primary amino group of hydrazide undergoes condensation with ketonic groups resulting the formation of hydrazones.

Starting from quinoline 8-thioglycollic acid hydrazide we have prepared unreported hydrazones